

1. RWM egg distribution sampled from 9 flooded, wet seedbeds, Zaragoza, Nueva Ecija, Philippines, 1984.

seedbeds (Fig. 2b), and therefore carry insignificant numbers of RWM eggs to the field. Most infestation, therefore, begins after transplanting. *S*

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2a. Wet seedbeds showing standing water between adjacent beds.

2b. Wet seedbeds after seedlings are pulled, leaving the borders.

Pest Control and Management DISEASES

Spread of rice tungro spherical virus (RTSV) in Bicol, Philippines

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Tungro (RTV) is a disease complex associated with rice tungro bacilliform virus (RTBV) and RTSV. Previous

studies showed that susceptible varieties with RTV symptoms were generally infected with both RTBV and RTSV and that those without symptoms often were infected only with RTSV.

To confirm the occurrence of RTSV and identify vector species, *Nephotettix virescens*, *N. nigropictus*, and *Recilia dorsalis* were collected from rice fields in Bicol, Philippines, in Feb and Mar 1985.

Vector populations were high, but RTV incidence was low or nonexistent. The vectors were allowed overnight inoculation access on TN1 seedlings in test tubes. All inoculated seedlings were tested in ELISA for RTBV and RTSV 14–21 d after inoculation.

In about 32 ha of rice fields in 7 municipalities, leaf samples were collected from some rice plants with

Infectivity of RTV vectors^a collected in rice fields in Bicol, Philippines, Feb and Mar 1985.

Location	Variety	RTV infection (%)	Stage of collected vectors	Vectors (no.) transmitting RTBV (B) and RTSV (S)											
				N. virescens				N. nigropictus				R. dorsalis			
				B+S	B	S	None	B+S	B	S	None	B+S	B	S	None
Cagsawa, Albay	IR42	0	Adult	1	2	0	31	0	0	0	60	1	0	0	2
			Nymph	0	0	0	8	0	0	0	17	-	-	-	-
Ligao, Albay	Masuri	5	Adult	0	0	3	26	0	0	2	9	-	-	-	-
			Nymph	1	0	3	14	0	0	0	1	-	-	-	-
Polangui, Albay	IR50/unknown	0	Adult	0	0	1	6	0	6	1	6	1	0	0	1
			Nymph	0	1	1	8	0	0	0	1	-	-	-	-
Pili Camarines Sur	IR29/IR58	0	Adult	0	0	0	1	0	0	7	64	-	-	-	-
			Nymph	-	-	-	-	0	0	0	2	-	-	-	-
San Fernando, Camarines Norte	Unknown	0	Adult	0	0	0	16	0	0	0	19	0	0	0	1
			Nymph	0	0	0	8	0	0	0	5	-	-	-	-
Daet, Camarines Norte	IR42	0	Adult	0	0	0	13	0	0	0	31	-	-	-	-
			Nymph	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	2	-	-	-	-
Talisay, Camarines Norte	IR42/unknown	0	Adult	1	0	0	24	0	0	0	44	-	-	-	-
			Nymph	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Total				3	3	8	156	0	0	10	261	2	0	0	4

^aField-collected vectors were allowed to feed on TN1 seedlings and the inoculated seedlings were tested in ELISA for RTV.

RTV-like symptoms and tested in ELISA. Leaf samples from Ligao municipality reacted positively to RTBV + RTSV and RTSV. Although the presence of RTV was not confirmed, some vectors collected in other municipalities transmitted RTBV + RTSV and RTSV (see table). At Pili, Camarines Sur, *N. virescens* populations

were very low, but *N. nigropictus* population was high. More than 10% of *N. nigropictus* transmitted RTSV.

Of 172 *N. virescens* tested, 3 transmitted RTBV + RTSV, 3 transmitted RTBV alone, and 8 transmitted RTSV. Of 271 *N. nigropictus* tested, 10 transmitted RTSV and none transmitted RTBV. Of six *R.*

dorsalis tested, two transmitted both viruses.

The results indicate that RTSV is spreading as an independent disease in Bicol and that both *N. nigropictus* and *N. virescens* are carriers. RTSV also occurs in rice fields where RTV incidence is very low or nonexistent. *J*

A new rice disease in Manipur, India

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A new rice disease has been identified in Manipur. The disease appears at panicle emergence, when the glume develops a whitish, powdery growth. If the infection occurs early, the grains become chaffy.

The pathogen was isolated from fresh, diseased glumes on potato dextrose

Susceptibility of panicles at different development stages to *Oospora*, Iroisemba, Manipur, India.

Panicle stage	Panicles inoculated (no.)	Panicles infected (no.)
Emerged	20	0
Milk	20	20
Dough	20	4
Mature	2	0

agar. Young panicles were inoculated with a 7-d-old culture of the pathogen. The pathogen was identified as *Oospora oryzaetorum*, which produces coenocytic, branched, hyaline mycelium. Conidia are hyaline. 1-celled, globose, and 2.3 ×

3.5 μ in diameter.

Panicles at different development stages were sprayed with mycelial bits and a spore suspension prepared from a 10-d-old culture. Milk stage was most susceptible to the disease (see table). *J*

Reaction of green leafhopper (GLH)-resistant varieties to rice tungro virus (RTV) complex

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We tested ARC11554, ASD7, Gam Pai 30-12-15, Gam Pai 30-12-30, Habiganj DW8, Jhingasail, Palasithari, and Ptb 18 for reaction to RTV-associated viruses. All the varieties except Habiganj DW8 were resistant to GLH. Single test plants were planted in clay pots and enclosed in mylar cages. One month after planting they were inoculated for

24 h with 1, 5, 10, 20, and 30 RTV viruliferous *Nephotettix virescens* per plant.

ARC1 1554, Habiganj DW8, and Ptb 18 had low infection with rice tungro bacilliform (RTBV) + rice tungro spherical (RTSV) viruses or RTBV alone, regardless of the number of GLH per plant. That indicated stability of their resistance to RTV complex. RTBV infection of ASD7, Gam Pai 30-12-15, Gam Pai 30-12-30, and Palasithari increased with the number of viruliferous GLH per plant (see figure). Jhingasail had mild yellowing and stunting but high RTBV + RTSV